

A ScaLAPACK-based Parallelization of LSDALTON

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Abstract

Linear Scaling DALTON (LSDALTON) is a powerful molecular electronic structure program that is the focus of software optimization projects in PRACE IIP-WP7.2 and PRACE IIP-WP7.5. This part of the project focuses on the introduction of parallel diagonalization routines from the ScaLAPACK library into the latest MPI version of LSDALTON. The parallelization work has involved three main tasks: i) Redistribution of the matrices assembled for the SCF cycle from a serial / distributed state to the two dimensional block-cyclic data distribution used for PBLAS and ScaLAPACK; ii) Interfacing of LSDALTON data structures to parallel diagonalization routines in ScaLAPACK; iii) Performance testing to determine the favoured ScaLAPACK eigensolver methodology.

1. Introduction to LSDALTON

Quantum chemistry applied to large molecular systems present a unique set of challenges. The LSDALTON program is designed to treat such systems efficiently and in a linear-scaling fashion by employing state-of-the-art methodology [1]. Ongoing developments in computer technology have highlighted the need for highly scalable computational software, both with respect to memory usage and computational cost. It has been the ambition of the current PRACE project to enable the LSDALTON code, comprising a little more than four hundred thousand lines of code, to take full advantage of contemporary supercomputer architectures. This is an ambitious undertaking, requiring that the algorithms are tailored to exploit parallelism on all levels of the code and, for our case, also to greatly reduce memory requirements. The LSDALTON program was initially based on the DALTON program [2], and despite the fact that the LSDALTON program no longer has any code in common with the DALTON program, the collaboration remains strong, evident by the fact that the two codes are today distributed together. The main strength of the LSDALTON program is the highly efficient and linear-scaling Hartree--Fock (HF) and Kohn--Sham (KS) Density functional theory (DFT) code suitable for large molecular systems, and the robust and efficient wave-function optimization procedures. The goal of this project is to develop a fully MPI/OpenMP hybrid parallelization scheme that can fully utilize the PRACE HPC installations, from the LSDALTON 2011 code.

2. Parallelisation Approach

The MPI parallelization approach adopted in the LSDALTON code can be categorized into two main strategies. For the integral evaluation we have developed our own strategy in which we minimize the MPI communication by dividing the computations into so-called tasks that rely on a priori predictions of the integral-evaluation cost. For the wavefunction-optimization and response-solver parts of the code, another strategy has been taken. These parts rely on pure matrix operations (multiplications, additions, trace, diagonalization and other simple operations), and are therefore obvious candidates to parallelize using externally developed libraries, like the ScaLAPACK library chosen here. Although the matrix operations are not typically the time-limiting factor of the LSDALTON code for serial calculations the computational time are in many applications still significant, especially for large molecular systems (comprising tens of thousands of basis functions). Additionally, calculations on large molecular systems are limited on most system architectures by their associated memory requirements,

which can easily reach 100 GB for calculations involving about one thousand atoms. It is therefore a crucial requirement to distribute the memory across all nodes, in order to perform large-scale calculations. In this project this has been achieved using PBLAS and ScaLAPACK.

3. Introduction of ScaLAPACK into LSDALTON.

The ScaLAPACK (Scalable Linear Algebra PACKage) library includes a subset of LAPACK routines redesigned for distributed memory MIMD parallel computers [3]. ScaLAPACK solves dense and banded linear systems, least squares problems, eigenvalue problems, and singular value problems. It requires that matrices are laid out in a two-dimensional block cyclic decomposition and invokes block-partitioned algorithms to ensure high levels of data reuse. Using a ScaLAPACK-based approach helps simplify the task of parallelizing high level routines by keeping the source code very similar to the sequential case (i.e. LAPACK). ScaLAPACK requires linking with two standard libraries (i) the BLAS, or Basic Linear Algebra Subprograms [4] and (ii) BLACS, or Basic Linear Algebra Communication Subprograms [5]. The main ScaLAPACK routine used here in LSDALTON is PDSYGVX for symmetric generalized eigensolves. Several other parallel matrix operations are undertaken in the code by PBLAS (Parallel Basic Linear Algebra Subprograms), which uses the same 2d block-cyclic distribution as ScaLAPACK [6].

The first step in the MPI parallelization of LSDALTON is the parallelization of the matrix operations. This has been achieved through the an interface with the PBLAS and ScaLAPACK libraries with the adding a matrix type:

```
TYPE Matrix
  !> number of rows
  INTEGER :: nrow
  !> number of columns
  INTEGER :: ncol
  !> number of rows
  INTEGER :: localnrow
  !> number of columns
  INTEGER :: localncol
  integer, pointer :: addr_on_grid(,:)
  real(REALK), pointer :: p(,:,:)
END TYPE Matrix
```

The second step is the MPI parallelization of the Coulomb, exchange correlation and one-electron integral contributions to the Fock / Kohn Sham matrix. The main focus by the LSDALTON developers has been on optimizing these steps, due to the much simpler interfacing to the SCALAPACK library for the matrix operations. As a consequence of these developments, the LSDALTON program is currently capable of performing MPI/OpenMP parallel non-Hybrid DFT calculations of molecules consisting of thousands of atoms.

The goal of the LSDALTON MPI parallelization is to achieve a fully distributed code. This means that the full matrices will never be on a single node, but are instead distributed among the available nodes. This approach will allow large-scale calculations on systems that are currently inhibited due to memory requirements. In order to achieve a fully distributed scheme the integrals must also be calculated in a memory distributed fashion and then directly transformed to the ScaLAPACK format. The ScaLAPACK matrix partitioning is not ideal for integral evaluation, so we have opted to instead build the integrals using our own memory-distributed format and to subsequently make a transformation to the ScaLAPACK format. This transformation has not yet been fully tested, and it is therefore still not certain if it poses a problem to scalability. This step therefore needs to be analyzed in the final part of this project.

4. Performance Results

We present some preliminary results for the ScaLAPACK-based LSDALTON implementation. A more thorough investigation of the LSDALTON performance will be presented in the final PRACE 1-iP WP7.2 whitepaper on LSDALTON. As an example (medium-sized) system we have run a single-point energy optimization for the Valinomycin molecule [7], using Kohn-Sham (KS) DFT with the BLYP functional and the 6-31+g* basis set (total of 168 atoms [C54H90N6O18] and 1584 basis functions)

The single-point calculation involved 20 self-consistent field (SCF) iterations for the KS density matrix optimization. During the course of each SCF iteration we construct a KS matrix from the density matrix (D) and perform an optimization step to obtain the density matrix of the next SCF iteration.

The KS matrix can be obtained in two ways, either exactly by combining regular Coulomb (reg-J) with exchange-correlation (xc) or by using the much more efficient density-fitting approximation for Coulomb (df-J) in combination with exchange correlation. We typically use the second ("fast") option instead of evaluating the exact integrals ("regular").

The density-optimization step (D-opt) involves both the transition from our own matrix format to a ScaLAPACK format, as well as the actual linear-algebra operations using ScaLAPACK (ScaLa). Note that we still have some overheads in the interface to ScaLAPACK, given as the difference between D-opt and ScaLa timings.

The ScaLAPACK matrix sizes are 1584 x 1584 for this example, and we have an adjustable block-size for ScaLAPACK based on the number of MPI nodes we use. The runs were undertaken on hardware nodes comprising of dual quad-core Xeons X5570 with a clock-speed of 2.93GHz with infiniband interconnect. Average timings per SCF iteration are given in seconds for the different contributions in the table below (see also the two attached figures):

Table 1. Average timings per SCF iteration in seconds for the different components (MPI only)

No. MPI Tasks	reg-J (secs)	df-J (secs)	xc (secs)	D-opt (secs)	ScaLa (secs)
1	6309	155.7	337.0	91.00	91.00
8	899.7	22.33	53.33	35.80	34.44
32	247.6	7.00	14.33	21.10	16.00
64	167.9	5.30	7.55	17.37	6.61
128	95.25	3.50	4.05	20.42	8.09

The pure MPI-based parallel results are presented in Table 1. The timings in the first three columns show that the construction of the KS matrix scales very well, with the preferred and faster df-J+xc method around 65 times faster than the serial code with 128 MPI tasks. The calculations involving ScaLAPACK (D-Opt) do not scale beyond 64 MPI tasks for this problem size, but is expected to scale better for larger matrices [8].

Table 2. Average timings per SCF iteration in seconds for the different components (MPI and OpenMP)

No. MPI Tasks / No. OpenMP Threads per MPI Task	reg-J (secs)	df-J (secs)	xc (secs)	D-opt (secs)	ScaLa (secs)
1 / 8	804.4	25.62	55.95	24.05	21.02
8 / 8	115.5	4.80	7.95	14.79	11.00
64 / 8	35.55	2.40	1.55	8.32	3.00
128 / 8	29.05	2.35	1.25	9.63	3.37

The mixed-mode performance results are presented in Table 2. It is shown that the construction of the KS matrix again scales very well up to 512 cores (64 / 8) but beyond this number, no significant further improvements are obtained from either construction approach. The parallel scaling of the calculations involving ScaLAPACK (D-Opt) is not as efficient, but continues to improve up to 512 cores.

Fig. 1 Performance speed-up of adding OpenMP threads for "regular" KS matrix build (using the reg-J + xc combination, see the text for details). All numbers relative to serial code performance

Fig. 2 Performance speed-up of adding OpenMP threads for "fast" KS matrix build (using the df-J + xc combination, see the text for details). All numbers relative to serial code performance

The performance results presented in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 measure the performance effect of adding OpenMP threads to MPI tasks on the Xeon-based nodes. All runs presented here use 8 OpenMP threads per MPI task and therefore fully occupy cores on the dual quad-core nodes. Ideal speed-ups would show a factor of 8 performance improvement for each mixed-mode combination. This level of scalability is almost achieved in runs with low MPI task counts, but higher MPI task counts show lower scaling ratios (the worst being a ratio of just over 2 for the 128 / 8 combination in the df-J calculation (Fig. 2)).

5. Conclusions & Future Work

In this project a hybrid MPI / OpenMP parallelisation scheme has been implemented into LSDALTON in order to exploit both current PRACE ccNUMA multicore architectures and expected future PRACE architectures, for example ccNUMA many-core. Utilizing ScaLAPACK proved to be a relatively quick way of parallelizing efficiently the computational core of a large-scale serial application code. The initial dataset tested here is relatively small (1584x1584) and the results have demonstrated scaling up to hundreds of cores. At the time of writing a fully distributed approach is not yet implemented and this is limiting both the parallel scaling and the problem size that can be calculated. Other PRACE studies [8] have recently shown that

ScaLAPACK is likely to scale up to several thousands of cores on PRACE Tier-0 systems when the problem size is made larger (e.g. of the order 5000-10000).

An upcoming PRACE-1IP WP7.2 whitepaper is expected to show more favourable timings for the ScaLAPACK interfacing, as by its delivery date, a fully distributed-memory scheme is expected to have been implemented in LSDALTON [9]. Also, performance analyses have helped identify various overheads associated with this first attempt at parallelization and these are currently being addressed.

Future work will focus on three main areas:

1. The MPI/OpenMP performance must be further analyzed and identified computational bottlenecks will be addressed in order to improve parallel performance.
2. The exact exchange contribution to the Fock/Kohn-Sham matrix will be parallelized and optimized.
3. The SCALAPACK interface will be optimized for typical LSDALTON applications.

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